

D5.1: Impact Assessment Methodology

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Contents

Executive summary.....	10
1. Introduction.....	11
1.1 ZeroW Project Summary.....	11
1.2 Deliverable purpose and scope	12
1.3 Mapping ZeroW outputs.....	14
1.5 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure	16
1.4 Relationship to other deliverables.....	16
1.5 Deliverable characteristics.....	17
1.6 Use of the Deliverable.....	17
2. Systemic Innovation.....	19
2.1 Short summary of the ZeroW SILLs	19
3. ZeroW SI Methodology - Three pillar approach	23
3.1 SI Assessment tool	23
4. Systemic Innovation Readiness Level.....	25
5. Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA)	27
5.1. Theoretical Background.....	28
5.2 Environmental footprint using LCA.....	28
5.2.1 Prospective LCA	29
5.2.2 Challenges to perform LCA on innovative emerging technologies	30
5.2.3 Goal and Scope of the study.....	30
5.2.4 Life Cycle Inventory Analysis.....	32
5.2.5 Life Cycle Impact Assessment.....	34
5.2.6 Interpretation.....	35
5.3. Social footprint analysis with SLCA	36
5.3.1 Steps of SLCA	38
5.4 Economic footprint analysis with LCC.....	40
5.5 Hotspot Analysis	43
5.6 LCSA in a nutshell	44
6. Cost Benefit Analysis and Balance	45
7. Data Collection	48

7.1 Different stages of data collection	48
7.2 Types of Data	50
7.3 Timeline of data collection in ZeroW	50
8. Conclusion	52
9. Annex I: SIRL Tools sample Questions	53
10. Annex II: Preliminary System Boundary of SILLs.....	54
11. Annex III: Template to calculate base value	59
12. Annex IV – Impact category for environmental footprint.....	69
13. Annex V – Sustainability Development Goals	71
14. Annex VI – Relevant Databases for LCA	72

List of figures

Figure 1 – ZeroW Project in a nutshell.....	11
Figure 2 – ZeroW Project approach and its elements	11
Figure 3 - Systemic Innovation Assessment.....	13
Figure 4 – Innovation readiness level	26
Figure 5 – Societal readiness level	26
Figure 6 - Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment	27
Figure 7 - Schematic overview of the challenges for the application of prospective LCA. Adapted from How to Conduct Prospective Life Cycle Assessment for Emerging Technologies ¹⁹	30
Figure 8 - Steps of LCA as described in ISO 14040 standard	32
Figure 9 - Background and Foreground Systems	34
Figure 10 – Example life cycle analysis of SILL 1, adapted from JRC technical Report, Domestic Footprint of the EU, and Member States: methodology and results (2010-2018).....	36
Figure 11 - Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (UN, 2015) pertinent on social issues and on governance towards Sustainable Development from a ZeroW perspective	37
Figure 12 - SLCA decision tree adapted from UNEP methodology ²⁷	38
Figure 13 - Stakeholder categories and subcategories in the UNEP 2020 Guidelines ²⁷	39
Figure 14 – Different cost profiles for LCC	41
Figure 15 – Methodological process for life cycle costing analysis	42
Figure 16 – Overall concept map of LCC detailing each step	42
Figure 17 - Eight key methodological steps for hotspot analysis.....	43
Figure 18 – Methodological steps for CBA in ZeroW	46

Figure 19 - Timeline for data collection	50
Figure 20 – Preliminary system boundary of SILL 1	54
Figure 21 - Preliminary system boundary of SILL 2.....	54
Figure 22 - Preliminary system boundary of SILL 3.....	55
Figure 23 - Preliminary system boundary of SILL 4.....	55
Figure 24 - Preliminary system boundary of SILL 5.....	56
Figure 25 - Preliminary system boundary of SILL 6.....	56
Figure 26 - Preliminary system boundary of SILL 7.....	57
Figure 27 - Preliminary system boundary of SILL 8.....	57
Figure 28 - Preliminary system boundary of SILL 9.....	58

List of tables

Table 1 Glossary of terms and acronyms used	8
Table 2 Adherence to ZeroW Grant Agreement deliverable and work description	14
Table 3 – Systemic innovation assessment tools	24
Table 4 – SLCA phases and their corresponding methods, adapted from Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessment of products and organizations 2020 social alliance	38
Table 5 - An overview of data collection in ZeroW	49

Glossary of terms and acronyms used

Table 1 Glossary of terms and acronyms used

Acronym / Term	Description
CBA	Cost Benefit Analysis
CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
EAP	Environment Action Programme
EC	European Commission
ERP	Enterprise Resource Planning
EU	European Union
F2F	Farm-to-Fork
FLW	Food Loss and Waste
FU	Functional Unit
GA	Grant Agreement
HR	Human Resource
IRR	Internal Return Rate
JRC	Joint Research Centre
JTM	Just Transition Mechanism
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Costing
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
LCIA	Life cycle impact assessment
LCSA	Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment
LCT	Life Cycle Thinking
MES	Manufacturing Execution System

NPV	Net Present Value
PEF	Product Environmental Footprint
OEF	Product Environmental Footprint
SC	Supply Chain
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SETAC	Society of Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry
SI	System Innovation
SILL	Systemic Innovations Living Labs
SIRL	Systemic Innovation Readiness Level
SLCA	Social Life Cycle Assessment
TBL	Triple Bottom Line
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme

Executive summary

This is the first deliverable (D5.1) of ZeroW Work Package 5 Systemic Innovation Assessment. This deliverable primarily reports the design, development, and deployment of an overarching methodology to assess the systemic innovation living labs (SILL). There are three assessment viewpoints – (a) the extent that the SILL innovations are improving during the project, (b) environmental, social, and economic impacts of the SILLs throughout their duration, and (c) the just transition elements of the innovations demonstrated.

The deliverable reports three high level tools which correspond to the above three assessment viewpoints – (a) Systemic innovation readiness levels (SIRL) (defined in Deliverable 4.1) are exploited to assess to the extent the SILL innovations are improving during the project lifetime, (b) Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment will be utilised to derive a holistic view of the environmental, social, and economic impacts of the SILLs, and (c) Cost benefit analysis will be utilised as a means to evaluate just transition elements. A detailed description of each of the tools along with data collection methodology from the SILLs are reported in this deliverable.

The methodology will be employed four times during the project life cycle (first round for baseline data collection from SILLs and three subsequent rounds of assessment), therefore it is dynamic and customisable in nature. Finally, the methodology contributes to the Impact 2 and 5 of ZeroW project.

1. Introduction

1.1 ZeroW Project Summary

The ZeroW project summary, including the aim and high-level approach is represented in Figure 1 and Figure 2 below.

Figure 1 – ZeroW Project in a nutshell

The ZeroW approach involves the following elements:

Figure 2 – ZeroW Project approach and its elements

1.2 Deliverable purpose and scope

The design, development, and deployment of an overarching methodology (shown in Figure 3) to assess the systemic innovation living labs of ZeroW is at the core of WP5 (Systemic Innovation Assessment). WP5 covers a period of M3-M48 and contains three tasks. The first task comprises of developing the methodology for assessing ZeroW systemic innovations. The second task is to perform assessment of SILL impacts, risks, sustainability trade-offs & level of 'just' allocation and the third task will perform a cluster-, place-, context-, actor- & gender-based interpretation of results. This deliverable is the outcome of the first task, containing a methodological guide to perform the innovation assessment of the ZeroW Systemic Innovations Living Labs (SILLs). The assessment methodology includes three assessment views: (i) the extent that the SILL innovations are improving during the project; (ii) the environmental, social, and economic impacts of the SILLs throughout their duration; (iii) the just transition elements of the innovations demonstrated. The methodology is highly customisable for the needs of the SILLs and will be exploited to answer to the questions: (a) which are the assessment indicators to be used; (b) what information will need to be collected from the SILLs; (c) how this information will be collected and who will provide it; (d) what are the potential information limitations to be faced. The methodology will also contribute to the assessment of (a) Impact 2 of ZeroW where the reduction of FLW related GHG emissions evaluated through GHG simulation using LCA and carbon footprint methodologies and (b) the impact indicators of Impact 5 will be evaluated through reduction in carbon footprint, positive results of LCSA, and economic cost/benefit ratio.

Figure 3 - Systemic Innovation Assessment

1.3 Mapping ZeroW outputs

Purpose of this chapter is to map ZeroW Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the current document.

Table 2 Adherence to ZeroW Grant Agreement deliverable and work description

ZeroW GA Component	ZeroW GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE D5.1			
D5.1 - Impact assessment methodology	Methodology for assessing ZeroW systemic innovations	Chapter 2-8	The methodology will assess the Systemic Innovation demonstrated in nine SILLs.
TASKS			
T5.1 - Methodology for assessing ZeroW systemic innovations	The methodology will address three assessment views: (i) the extent that the SILL innovations are improving during the project, by using the Systemic Innovation Readiness Levels (SIRLs) defined in D4.1; (ii) the environmental, social, and economic impacts of the SILLs throughout their duration, using Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA). The LCSA combines environmental life cycle assessment (LCA), life cycle costing (LCC), and social life cycle assessment (S-LCA). This assessment view will embed impacts 1-7, as defined in section 2.1;	All	The impact assessment methodology of ZeroW has been presented in section 1.3.2. T5.1 will further define it in detail and will adapt it to the specific conditions of each SILL. The methodology will address three assessment views: (i) the extent that the SILL innovations are improving during the project, by using the Systemic Innovation Readiness Levels (SIRLs) defined in T4.1; (ii) the environmental, social, and economic impacts of the SILLs throughout their

ZeroW GA Component	ZeroW GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
	(iii) the just transition element of the SILL innovations, using the LCSA results.		<p>duration, using Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA). The LCSA combines environmental life cycle assessment (LCA), life cycle costing (LCC), and social life cycle assessment (S-LCA). This assessment view will embed impacts 1-7, as defined in section 2.1; (iii) the just transition element of the SILL innovations, using the LCSA results. The methodology will also provide answers to the questions: which are the assessment indicators to be used? what information will need to be collected from the SILLs? how will this information be collected and who will provide it? what are the potential information limitations to be faced? In this Task, DIGI will also lead the implementation of the methodologies in a digital tool to allow all project partners to use it remotely and digitally in a post COVID-19 world. This ZeroW tool will extend the European Platform on LCA that provides guidance and data to facilitate life cycle impact assessment.</p>

1.5 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

In this section, we describe how the report is related within ZeroW to some other deliverables, and we outline the structure of the remainder of the report.

Chapter 1 includes an overview of the project objectives, deliverable mapping against other the work packages and deliverable's characteristics and use.

Chapter 2 explains the Systemic innovation along with concise description about the SILL's objectives.

Chapter 3 presents the ZeroW three pillar methodological approach with assessment tools.

Chapters 4, 5, 6 focus on the sustainability as aspect of the SILL.

Chapter 7 describes a methodology of data collection during the assessment.

1.4 Relationship to other deliverables

To reach its goals, ZeroW is divided into 11 WPs with different goals, tasks, and deliverables. This deliverable presents the methodology to assess Systemic Innovation (SI). This assessment is based on a multi-dimensional decision-making approach since it allows for overcoming the current limitations of innovation assessment. The methodology is the foundation for the impact assessment related tasks to be performed in WP5. It presents a set of complementary tools and processes, which enables the comprehensive assessment of innovation readiness, impact and just transition.

This deliverable is connected to previous deliverables, such as:

- Deliverable D1.1 "FLW conceptual model" that provides a conceptual framework for food loss and waste (FLW), a collective understanding of what is and what is not considered FLW, as well as provide an overview of the food system actors and dynamics behind FLW and interventions to reduce or reuse FLW,
- D4.3 SILL Strategic Plans that presents an Official Strategic Plans of all nine Systemic Innovation Living Labs (SILLs), with some analytical overviews on the status of SILLs, and
- D4.1 "Systemic Innovation maturity gaps" that provides the Systemic Innovation Readiness Level SIRL tool to incorporate several innovation dimensions into their FLW solution building and monitor the systemic innovation readiness level of their FLW solution throughout the project.

The methodology developed and reported in this deliverable will be utilised in Tasks 5.2 and 5.3. Therefore, the Deliverables 5.2 (SILL impacts assessment) and 5.3 (results interpretation) are directly build on top of this deliverable. Further to that the results of D5.1 will flow into (a) D6.2 FLW capacity building which will present

activities, material & tools for appropriation value from FLW innovations, (b) D7.2 Customer Validation & Solution Alignment in terms of long term sustainability, and (c) D8.2 Just transition pathway and intermediate targets to near-zero FLW by 2050.

1.5 Deliverable characteristics

Customizable: The methodology is highly adaptive, and it is possible to implement it in different SILLs. Each SILL has unique objectives inside the FLW supply chain, and the methodology can adapt to each SILL's specific conditions.

Agile: The methodology is created following an agile and lean methodology which enables flexibility and feedback mechanism keeping in mind the complexity of the project structure.

Quantitative and qualitative: The results are presented in quantitative and qualitative form, fulfilling the best possible evaluation.

Comprehensive: The methodology considers all aspects of the life cycle analysis (environmental, social, economic) and supports the SILLs in each stage of SI process.

Standardization and interoperability: The methodology follows ISO standards 14040¹, 14044² and is interoperable during use in different SILLs.

Quality Analysis: It incorporates quality assurance at the level of data collection and data management (described further in ZeroW D11.2 Data Management Plan) and internal and external review of the methodology.

Four-stage assessment: The methodology will be used four times during the project life cycle (first round for baseline data collection from SILLs and three subsequent rounds of assessment), therefore it is a living document and dynamic in nature.

1.6 Use of the Deliverable

The methodology will be applied 4 times during the project duration. First, parts of it will be used to collect the baseline data for each of the SILLs. Then there will be **three assessments taking place between M13 and M41, corresponding to SILLs evaluation rounds**. Those will result in 3 deliverable versions of D5.2: SILLs impact assessment.

Initial assessment (D5.2, internal version 1, M24)

Baseline data from all SILLs will be collected during M9-M12 following the data collection (Section 7) and reported in this deliverable. The methodology will then be

¹ ISO 14040:2006 Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Principles and framework, accessible online at <https://www.iso.org/standard/37456.html>

² ISO 14044:2006 Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Requirements and guidelines, accessible online at <https://www.iso.org/standard/38498.html>

exploited for an initial impact assessment corresponding to the first round of evaluation of the SILLs. It is primarily based on data collected from SILLs during the first round of evaluation, literature, assumption, simulation etc. This initial assessment will be compared with the baseline data. Note that, it will not be a full-scale assessment as specific KPIs might be left out due to lack of understanding or unavailability of quality data.

Mid-term assessment (D5.2, internal version 2, tentatively M36)

This assessment will correspond to the second evaluation round of the SILLs. With improved visibility and data from SILLs operations, mid-term assessment aims to provide a full-scale assessment and aids the decision-makers in the optimisation of systemic innovations.

Final assessment (D5.2, final version, M46)

The final assessment aims to be the most comprehensive full-scale impact assessment of all SILLs with future recommendations.

2. Systemic Innovation

SI is a type of innovation where value can be found in the synergy with other correlating innovations, having an objective to go beyond the boundaries of a single organization and advancing a collective approach. Therefore, the term 'systemic' refers to a collaborative innovation system³. All the former advancements made in the previous years had limited evidence on how to reduce FLW along the whole food supply chain, and even less on how to achieve a 'fair' impact across supply chain actors. What is still missing is testing and assessment of the systemic innovations⁵. Therefore, ZeroW envisions reducing FLW by employing systemic innovation through nine Systemic Innovation Living Labs (SILLs). This SI approach is based on the development of a core demonstrative environment supporting along the value chain, complemented by assessment activities to ensure a long term environmental and economic sustainability of zero-FLW (0FLW) solutions and a just transition towards a near-zero FLW system.

2.1 Short summary of the ZeroW SILLs

There are nine SILLs that will be demonstrating SI during the project lifetime. This section is based on the ZeroW D4.3 - SILLs Strategic Plans.

SILL 1- F2F FLW monitoring & assessment

- Objectives: (i) To deliver and pilot an open, data-driven IT-based solution for capturing FLW data throughout the supply chain and providing analytics to address the requirements of the SDG Indicator 12.3.1 (Global Food Loss and Waste), the Delegated Decision (EU) 2019/1597 and the Implementing Decision (EU) 2019/2000; (ii) To demonstrate the FLW monitoring & assessment solution in two EU countries to ensure its applicability and replicability in different business and cultural settings.
- End product/ service: Open, data-driven IT platform for FLW monitoring & assessment. End users: Food producers/processors, food retailers, consumers, HoReCa sector, kindergartens, schools, nursing homes, policy makers, solution providers (SMEs, start-ups).

SILL 2 - Innovative sustainable and smart packaging for fresh food products

- Objectives: (1) to demonstrate the use of a combined intelligent-functional-sustainable packaging solution, combining biobased & biodegradable materials, packaging design and freshness indicators (intelligent label) to significantly reduce food waste and unsustainable packaging at the retail and

³ Midgley, Gerald & Lindhult, Erik. (2017). What is Systemic Innovation?

consumer levels; (2) to demonstrate the use of a software for reading freshness colour changes of the intelligent packaging and transforming them into remaining shelf life, to allow retailers better manage their stock and reduce food waste.

- End product/ service: (a) Barrier and compostable packaging suitable for food contact; (b) Functional packaging based on a compartmentalised compostable tray retaining exudates liquids from fish and increasing quality; (c) App and freshness indicators for extending packaged fish shelf life and improving stock management at retail level. End users: Packers, retailers, and consumers.

SILL 3 - Wasteless greenhouse solutions for (pre)harvesting aligned with short-term downstream demand

- Objectives: To demonstrate innovations for food loss reduction at the pre-harvest and harvest stages of fruit & vegetable greenhouse farms through: (i) novel remote sensing solutions enabling accurate crop monitoring, fruit ripeness assessment & yield estimation; (ii) automated produce quality evaluation and estimation of 'substandard' produce at the pre-harvest and harvest stages; (iii) data-driven optimisation of combined harvest scheduling and short-term predicted downstream demand.
- End product/ service: (a) Technology for greenhouse fruit & vegetable growth monitoring, ripeness assessment and yield forecasting (initially focused on tomatoes), based on novel 'deep vision' and data science techniques; (b) Technical solution for automated produce quality evaluation according to 'cosmetic standards' at the pre-harvest and harvest stages; (c) Software service for optimal harvest scheduling, yield planning and data integration throughout the food supply chain. End users: Greenhouse fruit & vegetable farmers (individual, cooperatives, associations), food logistics & export service providers, food manufacturers, retailers.

SILL 4 - Mobile food valorisation as a service

- Objectives: (i) to demonstrate innovative, flexible, and versatile solutions as a service for optimising the use of edible biomass (fresh produce and edible fractions); (2) to demonstrate the economic viability of the business model applied and how the revenues will be distributed throughout the new value chains.
- End product/ service: (a) Mobile processing unit as a service; (b) Healthy, tasteful products derived from saved food and vegetable waste biomass; (c) Deteriorating food auctioning service. End users: Farmers, fruit & veg

auctions, processors, ingredient suppliers, tech providers, retailers, consumers.

SILL 5 - Ugly food early identification, shelf-life assessment & alternative valorisation

- Objectives: (i) to assess the shelf-life and compliance of products to retail requirements (e.g. shape, size, ripeness, defects) at an early stage, by non-destructive analysis and multi-attribute classification techniques, applied to a single fruit/vegetable or to a whole lot/batch; (ii) to use the shelf-life and compliance assessment to reduce FLW at the producer and the retailer side; (iii) to ensure quality products with a known shelf-life at the retailer side, providing market strategies for ugly food and optimise logistics/storage management.
- End product/ service: (a) Multi-sensor platform with capacity of analysing and processing around 300,000 fruit / hour and with the possibility of classification in three different outputs based on quality and shelf-life parameters; (b) Data service platform to control input produce. End users: Food processors, retailers.

SILL6- Food waste reduction through advanced data-driven production process control & optimisation

- Objectives: (i) to significantly reduce food loss in breaded poultry production (most complex line in the factory, with reference products, cordon bleu, 'Flamenquin') through a continuous advanced control & optimisation of the key variables and dynamics impacting processes involved, for intermediates and the final product; (ii) to migrate from a human-based, low-automation and reactive, to a data-driven, fully controlled, proactive and optimised system; (iii) to integrate the developed solution in the current Manufacturing Execution System (MES) and Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) system of ALDELIS avoiding information silos.
- End product/ service: Control and optimisation software platform for food production lines, to be offered through a Service Level Agreement or as a SaaS model. End users: Food processing SMEs.

SILL7- Food waste reduction through efficient food bank networks

- Objectives: (i) to demonstrate innovative solutions that strengthen the role of foodbanks as food waste reduction players; (ii) to help European food banks to professionalise their operations, and as such to reduce food losses throughout the food chains, while at the same time helping more people that are hungry in Europe; (iii) to make foodbank-centred food chains not only

more efficient, but at the same time also more just; (iv) to ensure that the conflicts between FLW reduction & food poverty, are adequately addressed.

- End product/ service: (a) demand prediction tool for European regions and food banks to assess the expected number of food bank customers; (b) supply prediction tool for food banks; (c) handbook of all possible food waste reduction strategies that foodbanks can adopt; (d) decision support tool for waste reduction initiatives at food banks; (e) donation tool for donors to advise on products that are ready for donation. End users: Consumers, NGOs, Food banks, Retailers, Municipalities.

SILL8- Retail food waste valorisation through algae production for high-value applications

- Objectives: (i) to develop an optimal and feasible solution for in-store and in-warehouse FLW pre-treatment (especially fruits & vegetables & animal proteins), addressing waste from stores (and equivalent premises); (ii) to characterise the pre-treated FLW and valorise it into the production of micro-algae; (iii) to develop a reverse logistics processes that takes into account safety regulations, business constraints, the complexity of FLW being decentralized in the retail context, and the use of an innovative hermetic container for transportation.
- End product/ service: (a) in-store/in-warehouse food waste pre-treatment process; (b) new hermetic container for FLW pre-treated transportation in reverse logistics; FLW logistics optimisation. End users: Retailers, algae producers, cosmetics producers, sustainable packaging producers.

SILL9- 'Fork to Farm to Fork' (3F): Informing and nudging consumers to make better choices through reverse (dietetics) and forward (FLW, sustainability, affordability) optimisation

- Objectives: (i) to develop recipes with low FLW, high nutritional score, and low environmental impact; (ii) to develop a food label and scores for FLW, nutritional value, and environmental impact, to trigger consumer behavioural change; (iii) to demonstrate the use of macro-scale optimisation models that balance FLW reduction with high nutritional value and food affordability
- End product/ service: (a) a label for meals, recipes & meal packages to inform the consumer about the meal's nutritional value as well as its impact on FLW and other environmental factors, and information on how to buy and store food responsibly to prevent FLW; (b) an app to allow consumers to obtain these scores for their own recipes or even for complete diets; (c) new recipes,

fresh meal packages & semi-prepared packets of ingredients, such as pre-cut vegetables developed to have a low impact on FLW, low environmental impact and high nutri-score. End users: Retailers, consumers.

The strategic plans that have been developed for the SILLs⁴ should be referred to for detail information about the SILLs.

3. ZeroW SI Methodology - Three pillar approach

The primary goal of the impact assessment methodology is to (a) assess the technical and investment readiness of the SI of the SILLs, (b) provide a holistic, transparent, factual analysis on environmental, social, and economic impacts, and (c) help them to refine the goal and scope during the lifetime. To perform the assessment, ZeroW takes a three-pillar approach harmonizing the existing innovation viewpoints by providing a comprehensive picture of the positive and negative impacts that each SILL's processes and services bring out.

The first pillar represents the **Systemic Innovation Readiness Level** (SIRL). It helps to assess the complete innovation readiness level of each SILL and identify which Scaling Readiness dimensions (Technological, Behavioural, Policy and Governance, Business, Value chain) are the most relevant measures of success and how to improve the SIRL, paving the way for systemic innovation commercialisation⁵.

The viewpoint of the second pillar is to perform a **Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment** (LCSA), incorporating LCA (Life Cycle Assessment) for the environmental impacts, LCC (life cycle costing) for the financial impacts and S-LCA (Social-LCA) for the social impacts.

The third pillar represents a **Cost-benefit analysis** to help to define a '**just**' **transition pathway** to near-zero FLW, including intermediate EU targets, and to deliver short- & medium-term FLW policy recommendations.

3.1 SI Assessment tool

In the ZeroW assessment methodology different tools (Table-3) will be used throughout the SILL's lifetime. Further details and explanation are given in the following chapters.

⁴ ZEROW Deliverable 4.3 – SILL Strategic Plans

Table 3 – Systemic innovation assessment tools

Phase	Tool	Why	How
Innovation Readiness	SIRL	Assess the readiness of the systemic innovation demonstrated in the SILLs	By using the SIRL tool developed in WP4 ⁵ .
Innovation Impact	LCA	To measure the environmental footprint and optimize the design, supply chain, material optimization.	Impact categories normalized, weighted, and aggregated according to ISO 14040 ⁶ .
	LCC	To measure the cost and enable to plan cost optimization.	Impact categories normalized, weighted, and aggregated according to ISO 14040
	S-LCA	Assess the social impacts and help the decision/policy makers, different stakeholders.	Impact categories normalized, weighted, and aggregated according to UNEP/SETAC SLCA methodology ⁷ developments.
	Hotspot Analysis	To identify the highest impacted area inside the value chain.	Following the 8 interactive steps proposed by SETAC ⁸
Just Transition	Cost-Benefit Analysis	To compare the economic benefits of an action or a decision versus the associated costs on social level, leading towards a just transition of food value chain and systems.	Exploiting the CBA calculator for assessment

⁵ ZEROW Deliverable 4.1: Systemic Innovation Maturity Gaps

⁶ ISO 14040:2006 - Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Principles and framework, available online at <https://www.iso.org/standard/37456.html>

⁷ UNEP/SETAC Life Cycle Initiative (2011), available online at - <https://www.lifecycleinitiative.org/wp-content/uploads/2012/12/2011%20-%20Towards%20LCSA.pdf>

⁸ Barthel, M., Fava, J., James, K., Hardwick, A. and Khan, S., 2017. Hotspots Analysis: An overarching methodological framework and guidance for product and sector level application. United Nations Environment Programme: Paris, France.

Phase	Tool	Why	How
			of food waste prevention developed by the EC ⁹ .

4. Systemic Innovation Readiness Level

SIRL is ZeroW’s main tool to assess the readiness of the systemic innovations introduced to and demonstrated in the SILLs. The SIRL has been developed in Task 4.1 and is based on the Scaling Readiness¹⁰ approach. The benefit of adopting such approach in the ZeroW assessment methodology is that scaling readiness not only assesses the maturity of technological innovations, but also of other types of innovations (e.g., social, and institutional innovations), which enable a significant broadening of scope when compared to technological readiness. Multiple ways of classifying these innovations have been investigated in ZeroW. The Deliverable 4.1⁵ of ZeroW reports several generic dimensions in this regard including technology, behavioural, policy & governance, business, and value chain.

Maturity scales are to be utilised to evaluate the readiness level of each SILL. These scales can be developed based on the general innovation readiness level (Figure 4) in order to be tailor-made to above-mentioned five dimension specific readiness levels (an example of a specific scale is presented in Figure 5). To exploit the SIRL assessment, the SILLs must agree on the key innovation dimensions of their systemic innovations are to be assessed. This is followed by evaluating how ‘ready’ the FLW solution of the SILL is about each separate dimension in the SI. The readiness level scales developed in ZeroW and the methodology of assessing the SILLs based on such scales are explained in detail in the Deliverable 4.1 and will be extensively utilised by WP5 tasks in assessing the SILLs.

⁹ Caldeira, C., De Laurentiis, V., Sala, S., Assessment of food waste prevention actions: development of an evaluation framework to assess the performance of food waste prevention actions, EUR 29901 EN; Luxembourg (Luxembourg): Publications Office of the European Union; 2019, ISBN 978-92-76-12388-0, doi:10.2760/9773, JRC118276

¹⁰ Sartas, M. et al. (2020) Scaling Readiness: Science and practice of an approach to enhance impact of research for development, *Agricultural Systems*, 183, 102874, ISSN 0308-521X.

IRLs	Description	Type of science	Type of evidence
0 Idea	Genesis of the innovation. Formulating an idea that an innovation can meet specific goal	None	None
1 Hypothesis	Conceptual validation of the idea that an innovation can meet specific goals and development of a hypothesis about the initial idea	Conceptual	Generic
2 Basic Model (unproven)	Researching the hypothesis that the innovation can meet specific goals using existing basic science evidence	Conceptual	Generic
3 Basic Model (proven)	Validation of the principles that the innovation can meet specific goals using existing basic science evidence	Basic science	Generic
4 Application Model (unproven)	Researching the capacity of the innovation to meet specific goals using existing applied science evidence	Basic science	Generic
5 Application Model (proven)	Validation of the capacity of the innovation to meet specific goals using existing applied science evidence	Applied science	Generic
6 Application (unproven)	Testing of the capacity of the innovation to meet specific goals within a controlled environment that reflects the specific spatial-temporal context in which the innovation is to contribute to achieving impact	Applied science	Generic
7 Application (proven)	Validation of the capacity of the innovation to meet specific goals within a controlled environment that reflects the specific spatial-temporal context in which the innovation is to contribute to achieving impact.	Applied science (controlled)	Specific to intervention context
8 Incubation	Testing of the capacity of the innovation to meet specific goals in natural/real/uncontrolled conditions in the specific spatial-temporal context in which the innovation is to contribute to achieving impact with support from an R4D	Applied science	Specific to intervention context
9 Ready	Validation of the capacity of the innovation to meet specific goals in natural/real/uncontrolled conditions in the specific spatial-temporal context in which the innovation is to contribute to achieving impact with support from an R4D	Applied science (uncontrolled)	Specific to intervention context

Figure 4 – Innovation readiness level

5-level scale	9-level scale
market launch	SRL9 - Actual solution <u>proven in relevant societal environments</u> after launch on the market; the society is using the solution available on the market
pre-market launch	SRL8 - <u>Targeted solution</u> , as well as a plan for societal adaptation, <u>complete and qualified</u> ; society is ready to adopt the solution and have used similar solutions on the market
Final stage of prototyping of the complete solution	SRL7 - <u>Refinement</u> of the solution and, if needed, <u>retesting in real world environments</u> with relevant stakeholders: the society is completely aware of the solution's benefits, a part of the society starts to adopt similar solutions
More and more extended inclusion of societal stakeholders (such as prospective users or other similar groups) in the testing, validation and demonstration phases of the R&D outputs	SRL6 - Solution <u>demonstrated in real world environments</u> and in co-operation with relevant stakeholders to gain feedback on potential impacts: the society knows the solution or similar initiatives and awareness of their benefits increases SRL5 - Solution <u>validated through pilot testing in real or realistic environments</u> and by relevant stakeholders: <u>the society knows the solution or similar initiatives but is not aware of their benefits</u> SRL4 - Solution <u>validated through pilot testing in controlled environments</u> to substantiate proposed impacts and societal readiness: a limited group of the society tests the solution or similar initiatives
Growing awareness of a R&D team about the existence of a societal readiness issue	SRL3 - <u>Initial sharing</u> of the proposed solution with relevant stakeholders (e.g. through visual mock-ups): a limited group of the society knows the solution or similar initiatives SRL2 - Formulation of proposed solution concept and potential impacts; <u>appraisal of societal readiness issues</u> ; identification of relevant stakeholders for the development of the solution SRL1 - <u>Identification</u> of the <u>generic societal need</u> and associated readiness aspects

Figure 5 – Societal readiness level

Concisely, each SILL will use the **SIRL as a continuous and iterative assessment tool** to evaluate the readiness levels of all dimensions of the systemic innovations and express concrete readiness progress ambitions and action plans. Such assessments of SILLs will also exhibit their system completeness to identify which Scaling Readiness (innovation) dimensions are the most relevant measures of success and how to improve the SIRL, paving the way for systemic innovation commercialisation. The SIRL will be used during the entire duration of the innovation process, as a monitoring tool, to continuously assess and steer innovation evolution. In Annex – I, the set of questions defined in D4.1 to identify the readiness level of the behavioural dimension are included for completeness of the current document as those will be used as part of the assessment of the SILLs.

5. Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA)

The impact of the systemic innovation demonstrated in the SILLs will be assessed using Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment¹¹, incorporating Life Cycle Assessment for the environmental impacts, life cycle costing for the financial impacts and Social Life Cycle Assessment for the social impacts. ZeroW project wants to achieve sustainability in the agri-food value chain through SI. Developing innovative sustainable solutions that are ready to be scaled up is a complex multi-dimensional phenomenon with a magnitude of complexity and trade-offs which cannot be covered by a one-dimensional approach. To broaden the SILLs' impact and deepen the analysis, three pillars of sustainability are considered: people, planet, and profit. The overarching life cycle sustainability assessment illustrates three sustainability dimensions, e.g., environmental, economic, and social. LCA deals only with the environmental or ecological component, while with the development of LCC¹² and SLCA, LCA broadened itself from the environmental assessment viewpoint to a more comprehensive life cycle sustainability assessment adopting life cycle thinking method.^{13,14} (portrayed in Figure 6) by including LCC and SLCA. While LCA is internationally standardised (ISO 14040 (2006) framework), the methodology and steps of LCC and SLCA are widely academically agreed upon but not yet standardised.

Figure 6 - Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment

¹¹ Guinée, J. (2016). Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment: What Is It and What Are Its Challenges? In: Clift, R., Druckman, A. (eds) Taking Stock of Industrial Ecology. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-20571-7_3

¹² Swarr, T.E., Hunkeler, D., Klöpffer, W., Pesonen, H.L., Ciroth, A., Brent, A.C. and Pagan, R., 2011. Environmental life-cycle costing: a code of practice. The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment, 16(5), pp.389-391.

¹³ Halog, A.; Manik, Y. Advancing Integrated Systems Modelling Framework for Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment. Sustainability 2011, 3, 469-499. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su3020469>.

¹⁴ Klöpffer, W. and Renner, I., 2008. Life-cycle based sustainability assessment of products. In Environmental management accounting for cleaner production (pp. 91-102). Springer, Dordrecht.

Concerning that, the ZeroW assessment methodology incorporates LCA as the most appropriate and robust assessment framework for the evolution of the potential environmental impact. However, products are also related to other stakeholders such as consumers, value chain actors, local community etc; and in this respect SLCA is an appropriate tool to evaluate social impacts. In addition to that, LCC includes the economic dimension to identify economic hotspots, which are valuable to the decision makers within a full sustainability assessment.

5.1. Theoretical Background

According to UNEP⁷, LCSA refers to evaluating all environmental, social and economic negative impacts and benefits in decision-making processes towards more sustainable products throughout their life cycle. The framework for LCSA initially proposed by Klöpffer and Renner¹⁴ was based on three life cycle approaches: Environmental Life Cycle Assessment (E-LCA) for the environmental perspective, Life Cycle Cost for the economic perspective, and Social Life Cycle Assessment¹⁵ for the social perspective. This initial approach has then evolved towards the UNEP/SETAC guidelines on performing LCSA. Also, Elkington¹⁶ explained that 'triple bottom line' (TBL) accounting attempts to relate the social and environmental impact of an organization's activities, measurably, to its economic performance in order to show improvement or to make evaluation more in-depth.' In that sense, TBL encourages an integrated approach of life cycle sustainability assessment, considering the three pillars of the environment, economy, and society.

The outputs of the LCSA for all SILLs will be compared, paving the way for assessing the levels of just allocation of costs, benefits, and risks among food value chain actors. This analysis will be further extended for select regions (covering the SILLs), following the Just Transition Mechanism (JTM) paradigm¹⁷, to also feed the scaling up strategies in WP6.

5.2 Environmental footprint using LCA

According to an EU JRC report¹⁸, the protection of the environment is one of the core principles of the EU and has been integrated in different EU policies. Assessing the

¹⁵ Guidelines for social life cycle assessment of products, available online at <https://www.lifecycleinitiative.org/wp-content/uploads/2012/12/2009%20-%20Guidelines%20for%20sLCA%20-%20EN.pdf>

¹⁶ <https://hbr.org/2018/06/25-years-ago-i-coined-the-phrase-triple-bottom-line-heres-why-im-giving-up-on-it>

¹⁷ The Just Transition Mechanism: making sure no one is left behind, available online at - https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal/finance-and-green-deal/just-transition-mechanism_en

¹⁸ Sala S., Beylot A., Corrado S., Crenna E., Sanyé-Mengual E, Secchi M. (2019) Indicators and Assessment of the environmental impact of EU consumption. Consumption and Consumer Footprint for assessing and monitoring EU policies with Life Cycle Assessment, Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, ISBN 978-92-79-99672-6, doi:10.2760/403263, JRC114814.

environmental impacts of consumption of goods and services is therefore of utmost importance to meet environmental objectives and targets set by the EU. The 7th Environment Action Programme (7th EAP) (European Parliament and Council, 2013)¹⁸, guiding EU environmental policies until 2020 has replaced the principle to live well within the ecological limits of our planet. To do so, resource efficiency must be addressed, measured, and improved¹⁸. In the context of FLW, measuring environmental impacts of consumption over time and the extent to which they are decoupling from economic growth is a key driver to assess the success of the abovementioned environmental policies (European Parliament and Council, 2013)¹⁸.

5.2.1 Prospective LCA

Following the definition provided by the EC, LCA is an internationally standardised methodology. It enables quantifying the environmental pressures related to goods and services (products), the environmental benefits, the trade-offs, and areas for achieving improvements considering the full life cycle of the product¹⁹. ZeroW envisions building several innovative technologies such as open data driven IT platform (SILL 1), Mobile application with freshness indicator (SILL 2) and remote sensing-based monitoring on tomato production in various stages, “deep vision” and data science techniques for yield forecasting (SILL 3) of the FLW value chain to reduce FLW. Therefore, a combination of conventional and prospective LCA will be incorporated in the assessment methodology. Traditionally, LCA has been used to assess mature and commercially scaled technologies, thus generating detailed inventory data. However, for the innovative solutions, there is no pilot mature enough for gathering inventory data. **Prospective LCA has been recently introduced to perform LCA in emerging technologies.** It has become a research area that promotes the integration of environmental criteria in early stages of technology development, which is conducive for responsible research and innovation.²⁰ It has been estimated that about 80% of all environmental effects associated with a product or process are locked-in during the design phase²⁰. Incorporating sustainability assessment from the very beginning of the project helps technology developers and decision makers to optimize the process. A ground research on 44 case studies^{Error! Bookmark not defined.} has been conducted on prospective LCA, showing that the most authors believes that prospective LCA is useful in a way that it provides new insights during the design and development of new emerging technologies, and can support developers, policymakers in their work. The results provide significant insight to the designer or process engineer to identify hotspots.

¹⁹[https://ec.europa.eu/environment/ipp/lca.htm#:~:text=Life%20Cycle%20Assessment%20\(LCA\)%20is,life%20cycle%20of%20the%20product.](https://ec.europa.eu/environment/ipp/lca.htm#:~:text=Life%20Cycle%20Assessment%20(LCA)%20is,life%20cycle%20of%20the%20product.)

²⁰ https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/publication/prospective-life-cycle-assessment-emerging-technologies-bio-based-materials_en

5.2.2 Challenges to perform LCA on innovative emerging technologies

Hetherington et al.²¹ has highlighted the challenges of using LCAs during the development of emerging technologies as shown in Figure 7. The challenges include comparability, scaling issue, data availability, data quality, and uncertainty. Comparability is a consequential issue performing LCA between mature technology and innovative technology. For example, SILL 1 is building a data-driven IT platform for reducing FLW across the local food value chain and the novel nature of the platform leads to several challenges related to the aim of the study, including understanding the functionality at the early stage, a clear system boundary and impact assessment. Furthermore, in a SI scenario, inventory data is scarce, causing innumerable uncertainty.

Figure 7 - Schematic overview of the challenges for the application of prospective LCA. Adapted from *How to Conduct Prospective Life Cycle Assessment for Emerging Technologies*^{Error! Bookmark not defined.}

5.2.3 Goal and Scope of the study

In compliance with ISO 14040, ZeroW's methodology includes four iterative processes for conducting LCA (Figure 8). The goal and scope for the assessment should be stated explicitly from the very beginning. For example, the reason behind carrying out the assessment, if any alternative solutions are already available in the market, the intended audience (e.g., primarily the SILL partners and later on the European citizens), etc. The goal of the ZeroW LCA is (a) to conduct a preliminary

²¹ Hetherington, A.C.; Borrión, A.L.; Griths, O.G.; McManus, M.C. Use of LCA as a development tool within early research: Challenges and issues across different sectors. *Int. J. Life Cycle Assess.* 2014, 19, 130–143.

assessment of the (expected) environmental impacts of current food chains in terms of FLW and identify the hotspots, (b) subsequently, to assess the potential environmental impact after using the ZeroW innovative solution and (c) finally, to identify the areas for improvement and evaluate optimisation suggestions.

In this first step, ZeroW LCA will model FLW from three points of view – (a) FLW conceptual model, (b) FLW economic model development & SILL-based validation, and (c) modelling the impact of FLW operational & policy interventions at the micro- (SC), meso- (food sector) and macro- (EU) levels.

System boundary

Defining the system boundary is a subjective choice along with the scope definition. It determines which unit processes would be included in the study. In ZeroW, SILLs are truly diverse with many stakeholders involved. Based on the objectives of each SILL given in the proposal, a primary system boundary has been made (Annex I). It will be further well-defined with more detailed steps along with SILL specific input outs as the SILLs become more mature in the life cycle (Task 5.2). During the system boundary definition phase, ZeroW will investigate the environmental inputs and outputs associated with the determined FLW economic models as well as FLW digitalization services & infrastructure, ZeroW system innovation tools, and SILL demonstrations.

Functional Unit

Function is the service provided by a system, thus defining a functional unit (FU) is a key element in LCA study. The functional unit, in a form of numerical value must be clearly defined and measurable; so that it can allow comparison based on the same reference flow. In a prospective LCA, multiple functional units, such as those containing possible additional functions, should be included. Multiple functional units can be tested in a sensitivity analysis in order to analyse the sensitivity that relies on the definition of the functional unit^{Error! Bookmark not defined.}. For example, a tonne of apple in Fox system in SILL 4 or five tonnes of tomato in remote sensing-based monitoring in SILL 3 can be the functional unit under consideration.

Figure 8 - Steps of LCA as described in ISO 14040 standard

5.2.4 Life Cycle Inventory Analysis

Life Cycle Inventory is a collection and analysis of environmental interventions data (e.g., emissions to air/water) associated with a product from the extraction of raw materials through production and use, to final disposal, including recycling, reuse, and energy recovery²². As inventory data, inputs going into the system (energy, material, water etc.) and outputs from the system (goods, waste, waste, emissions, co-product) should be collected. The scarcity of data exists in conventional LCAs, but in prospective LCAs for emerging technologies, this issue is exacerbated, leading to uncertainty and delay in the assessment²³. For the LCI, primary data like expert interviews should be first used, and if no primary data is accessible, secondary or proxy data, e.g., from the literature, should be used.

In this step, environmental impacts will be classified and evaluated based on the ZeroW objectives & targets, and translated into themes (i.e., hotspots, which are outlined below) including global warming, circular economy, Just Transition, human health, and overall Green Deal objectives.

Data quality requirements

Having excellent quality data in the LCA is essential. Practitioners often encounter several inconsistencies related to data such as data age, laboratory scale data,

²² <https://ec.europa.eu/environment/ipp/lca.htm>

²³ Arvidsson, R.; Tillman, A.-M.; Sandén, B.A.; Janssen, M.; Nordelöf, A.; Kushnir, D.; Molander, S. Environmental Assessment of Emerging Technologies: Recommendations for Prospective LCA: Recommendations for Prospective LCA. *J. Ind. Ecol.* 2018, 22, 1286–1294.

incompleteness, regional or small-scale implementation, wrong assumptions etc. Securing that issue, ISO 14040 has standardized the quality of data.²⁴

- ✓ Time-sensitivity: what time should the data represent? It is recommended to use data from last 5 years.
- ✓ Geographical coverage: what geographical area or region should the data represent? Does that match with the goal and scope?
- ✓ Technology coverage: For the included processes, what is the level of technology used to produce materials and products? The best available technology for the process should be used.
- ✓ Precision, completeness, and representativeness of the data
- ✓ Consistency and reproducibility that matches the procedure
- ✓ Data source: From which sources should data be collected? For example, data can be collected from the farm, warehouse, information lab, local authority, commercial LCA databases, etc.
- ✓ Uncertainty of the information and data gaps, how should uncertainties in data and data gaps be handled?

In an adequate dataset these items should be included.

Methodology for inventory data collection

Collecting inventory data can be tedious and time consuming. Here is a guideline to proceed with the inventory data collection for conducting LCA.

- Draw a process flow diagram that outlines all the unit processes to be modelled, including their interrelationships
- Describe each unit process in detail with respect to factors influencing inputs and outputs
- List all flows and relevant data for operating conditions associated with each unit process
- Determine an appropriate flow for each unit process and then calculate the quantitative input and output data of the unit process in relation to this flow
- Based on the system flow chart between all the unit processes, calculate the inputs and outputs of all unit processes related to the reference flow / functional unit proceed with inventory data collection.

Data will also be classified later in the process. The aim of this process is to have a list of all system input and output data referenced to the functional unit.

A detailed data collection guide is given in Section 7. WP5 will coordinate with SILLs' coordinators and liaise with WP4 to collect data.

²⁴ <https://www.iso.org/standard/37456.html>

Background and Foreground System

During the inventory data collection, it is useful to separate the “foreground” and “background” systems (demonstrated in Figure 9). The foreground system is the principal set of unit processes that directly impact the study, delivering a functional unit specified in Goal and Scope Definition. The background system consists of processes that have maximum indirect influence is exercised by the policymakers in the study. Normally, via a homogeneous mark, differentiation between foreground and background systems is important for deciding on what kind of data should be used.

For example, operational data that will come from all the SILLs is foreground data, whereas the data that comes from the pilot site reflecting local, regional, and national level, is background data. If it is not possible to collect these data due to lack of availability or complex structure, ZeroW will utilise an appropriate European standard as guidance.

Figure 9 - Background and Foreground Systems

5.2.5 Life Cycle Impact Assessment

Once the data is collected by using different emissions and varied materials (such as soil, fertilizer, pesticides), the impacts can be quantified. ZeroW methodology will follow the 16 standard indicators standardized by ISO 14040 (A complete list of indicators is given in Annex IV). For example, to find out the Climate Change potential, gases such as CO₂, CH₄, Ozone, NO₂ being present in the atmosphere absorb and emit radiation, trap heat from the sun etc will be measured.

During early discussions with SILLs, several impact categories have been identified which include – (a) abiotic depletion, which is related to consumption of non-living resources, (b) human toxicity potential which indicates the potential harms to humans from chemicals being used in SILLs, and (c) how much the land is being

used. So, all these categories based on all the emissions that is coming out due to all activities being performed. The first stage is to select impact categories which are relevant for each SILL. For example, SILL1 has chosen the impact category which are most crucial for them are climate change, ozone depletion, land use, water use, resource use minerals etc. Due to the existence of different techniques and units, a normalization and single score method is recommended while performing LCA. Normalisation and weighting are frequently practised in ascertaining important impact categories, comparing the results with industry or literature references, and solving trade-offs in results. After the impact category, it is the end point damage categories that then would be connected to such as human health, resource depletion, ecosystem quality etc (Annex -IV).

5.2.6 Interpretation

This is the last stage of LCA where the LCIA results will be summarised, analysed and recommendations provided in accordance with the goal and scope of the study. After conducting an LCA, recommendations of choices that are more impactful can be given to the SILLs. The SILL partners can take a close look at the how the footprint can be reduced by optimizing the design or process or by building a different supply chain and how they can make a difference in terms of environmental impact.

LCA is an iterative process, meaning that at any stage of the process the practitioner can go back, analyse, and repeat the process. In the ZeroW context, this tool is expected to be most robust and useful to achieve sustainability. The interpretation phase shall include (1) a completeness check ensuring that all the relevant information and data for the interpretation are available and complete, (2) a consistency check to make sure that the assumptions, methods, data are consistent with the goal and scope of the study, and (3) a sensitivity check in order to see the influence of the most important assumption followed by change the assumption and recalculate LCA. Also, identification of the hotspots, estimation of uncertainty, conclusions, limitations, and recommendations are an integral part of the interpretation process.

An example of the above four steps of performing LCA on SILL 1 is shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10 – Example life cycle analysis of SILL 1, adapted from JRC technical Report, Domestic Footprint of the EU, and Member States: methodology and results (2010-2018)²⁵

5.3. Social footprint analysis with SLCA

The ZeroW SI assessment will undertake a schematic methodological approach based on the UNEP/SETAC methodology²⁶ to measure the social impacts. S-LCA is a tool to assess the social impacts of products and services across their lifecycle. With a systematic technique, it offers a framework that combines quantitative as well as qualitative data which is sustainable from a social and socio-economic perspective leading to the prospect to improve the social outlook of an organization and the

²⁵ Sanyé Mengual, E; Tosches, D; Sala, S, Domestic Footprint of the EU, and Member States: methodology and results (2010-2018), EUR 30796 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2022, ISBN 978-92-76-40828-4, doi:10.2760/441655, JRC125941.

²⁶ UNEP, 2021. Methodological Sheets for Subcategories in Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) 2021. Traverso, M., Valdivia, S., Luthin, A., Roche, L., Arcese, G., Neugebauer, S., Petti, L., D'Eusanio, M., Tragnone, B.M., Mankaa, R., Hanafi, J., Benoît Norris, C., Zamagni, A. (eds.). United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP)

well-being of stakeholders. The reason behind incorporating S-LCA in the methodology is to assess the socio-economic impacts along the SILLs' life cycles, complementing the E-LCA. In the value chain SLCA focuses on the "people" side from a ZeroW stakeholder perspective and inform the decision makers, policy makers, enterprises, consumers. Unlike E-LCA, SLCA is still in its infancy, which being the case it requires clear clarification including handling two hundred social indicators²⁷.

Relevance to sustainable development

SLCA has an indispensable relation with the 2030 agenda for sustainable development, adopted by all United Nations Member States in 2015 as 17 SDG which are an urgent call for action by all countries. The SDGs relevant to the people pillar of the triple bottom line are presented in Figure 11 and a full list is given in Annex – V. Also, there are international instruments involved in developing S-LCA such as European Convention on Human Rights (Article 14 – Prohibition of discrimination; Protocol 12, Art. 1 – General Prohibition of discrimination), Treaty on Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture etc²⁶.

Figure 11 - Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (UN, 2015) pertinent on social issues and on governance towards Sustainable Development from a ZeroW perspective

²⁷ Swarr, T.E., Hunkeler, D., Klöpffer, W., Pesonen, H.L., Ciroth, A., Brent, A.C. and Pagan, R., 2011. Environmental life-cycle costing: a code of practice. *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*, 16(5), pp.389-391. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1065/lca2006.08.261>

5.3.1 Steps of SLCA

SLCA also follows the ISO framework 14040, accordingly its methodology follows similar steps like the LCA (Table 4 and Figure 12) -

- Goal and Scope
- Life cycle inventory
- Life cycle impact assessment
- Interpretation

Table 4 – SLCA phases and their corresponding methods, adapted from Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessment of products and organizations 2020 social alliance²⁸

S-LCA phases	Type of instrument, reference, or method
Goal and Scope	International policy framework, codes of conduct and principles, sustainability reporting frameworks, Implementation Guidelines
Life cycle inventory	Sustainability reporting frameworks, auditing and monitoring frameworks and financial indices, social impact assessment
Life Cycle Assessment	International policy framework
Interpretation	International policy framework, Implementation guides, Sustainability reporting guidelines

Figure 12 - SLCA decision tree adapted from UNEP methodology²⁸

²⁸ UNEP, 2020. Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessment of Products and Organizations 2020. Benoît Norris, C., Traverso, M., Neugebauer, S., Ekener, E., Schaubroeck, T., Russo Garrido, S., Berger, M., Valdivia, S., Lehmann, A., Finkbeiner, M., Arcese, G. (eds.). United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP)

Selection of stakeholders and subcategories

SLCA takes a stakeholder driven approach where the potential impacts on different stakeholder categories are considered and studied. Therefore, assessing the social performance requires that all the indicators will be related to stakeholders. A comprehensive list of stakeholders with subcategories are shown in Figure 13, furthermore SLCA has more than 200 indicators. For example, SILL1 has initially chosen the following stakeholders: Local community and Value chain actors.

A detailed selection of stakeholders, subcategories and indicators followed by survey questions will be developed in Task 5.2 in alliance with all the SILL partners.

Stakeholder categories	Worker	Local community	Value chain actors (not including consumers)	Consumer	Society	Children
Subcategories	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Freedom of association and collective bargaining 2. Child labor 3. Fair salary 4. Working hours 5. Forced labor 6. Equal opportunities/discrimination 7. Health and safety 8. Social benefits/social security 9. Employment relationship 10. Sexual harassment 11. Smallholders including farmers 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Access to material resources 2. Access to immaterial resources 3. Delocalization and migration 4. Cultural heritage 5. Safe and healthy living conditions 6. Respect of indigenous rights 7. Community engagement 8. Local employment 9. Secure living conditions 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Fair competition 2. Promoting social responsibility 3. Supplier relationships 4. Respect of intellectual property rights 5. Wealth distribution 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Health and safety 2. Feedback mechanism 3. Consumer privacy 4. Transparency 5. End-of-life responsibility 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Public commitments to sustainability issues 2. Contribution to economic development 3. Prevention and mitigation of armed conflicts 4. Technology development 5. Corruption 6. Ethical treatment of animals 7. Poverty alleviation 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Education provided in the local community 2. Health issues for children as consumers 3. Children concerns regarding marketing practices

Figure 13 - Stakeholder categories and subcategories in the UNEP 2020 Guidelines²⁸

There are several challenges and limitations involved in SLCA.

- Collecting quantitative data is challenging without any standard.
- Each SILL has different partners, in a situation like that access to the organizational data from each partner can be extremely difficult, additionally the average data published do not represent the real situation.
- For a diverse framework like SILLs there is a variety of resources related to related categories, making the generic datasets more difficult.
- Organizations might not provide sensitive information like wage, gender ratio etc.
- While labels are useful way to communicate transparency to consumers, some labels have standards and some not which leads to confusion.

To overcome these challenges WP5, in liaison with WP4 will guide and educate all the SILLs to collect inventory data. SILLs are comprised of diverse partners, consequently all partners from each SILL will be involved in the data collection process. Individuals who have a thorough understanding of different kinds of policy documents on human rights and workers' rights, gender case studies at an European level can be involved. In addition to that, spreading an awareness to different value chain actors can also help to gather quantitative data.

LCA and SLCA are both grounded in life cycle thinking but unlike environmental LCA which tend to show a negative result, SLCA can provide some positive impacts such as redistribution of food through an optimized method developed (SILL 5).

5.4 Economic footprint analysis with LCC

LCC assesses the economic performance of a product or a service over its lifetime. The LCC analysis balances the initial financial investment with the long-term ownership and operational investments. In other words, the methodology of performing LCC consists of estimating the total cost of a product or service, considering its whole life cycle, direct and external costs (e.g., material acquisition, annual costs of operations & maintenance, decomposition costs at the end-of-life cycle)²⁹. Businesses and Governments often perform LCC analysis to select the most cost-effective (i.e., least cost) approach among various product alternatives to achieve the lowest long-term cost of ownership³⁰. This is evident in the public tendering prospect of the EU. Under the 2014 EU procurement rules, a contract must be awarded based on the most economically advantageous tender³¹.

The LCC based assessment will provide several insights³² which have been adapted for each SILL of ZeroW –

- Evaluation and analysis of any alternative food value chain and system in innovation design and development.
- Assessment of economic viability of the SILL products and services.
- Identification of cost drivers of SILLs and possible cost-effective improvements and optimisations.

²⁹ L. E. Greene and B. L. Shaw, "The steps for successful life cycle cost analysis," IEEE Conference on Aerospace and Electronics, 1990, pp. 1209-1216 vol.3, doi: 10.1109/NAECON.1990.112942.

³⁰ Ali M. Eltamaly, Mohamed A. Mohamed, Chapter 8 - Optimal Sizing and Designing of Hybrid Renewable Energy Systems in Smart Grid Applications, Editor(s): Imene Yahyaoui, Advances in Renewable Energies and Power Technologies, Elsevier, 2018, Pages 231-313, ISBN 9780128131855, <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-813185-5.00011-5>.

³¹ Life cycle costing by the European Commission, available online at - <https://ec.europa.eu/environment/gpp/lcc.htm>

³² Reffat, R.M., Gero, J. and Peng, W., 2004, November. Using data mining on building maintenance during the building life cycle. In Proceedings of the 38th Australian & New Zealand Architectural Science Association (ANZASCA) Conference (pp. 91-97).

- Evaluation and comparison of any alternative strategy for systemic innovation deployment, operationalisation, and maintenance for SILLs.
- Evaluation and comparison of different approaches for replacement, extension, or disposal of aging infrastructure used by any SILL.
- Long term financial planning for economic sustainability for SI scale up for all SILLs. Optimal allocation of available funds to such scale up and operational sustainability activities will be further analysed during the cost-benefit analysis leading to JTM for all SILLs.

In ZeroW, the methodology for performing the LCC based assessment covers six iterative steps as shown in Figure 15 –

- Goal & scope definition (or problem definition)
- Cost elements definition (since there are several types of costs involved in the SILLs like fixed cost, variable cost, external cost etc) (Figure 14).
- System modelling (for each SILL)
- Data collection from SILLs
- Cost profile development
- Evaluation

Fixed cost	
	Investment and interest
	Maintenance
	Cost of staff
	Other: cost of permits, contracted costs and overhead e.g. R&D
Variable cost	
	Energy
	Raw materials
	Auxiliaries
	Waste management
	Transportation
	Revenue from by-products (income)

Figure 14 – Different cost profiles for LCC

Figure 15 – Methodological process for life cycle costing analysis

Each of the above steps can be further broken down into sub-steps realising a concept map (shown in Figure 16) of the LCC assessment that ZeroW will undertake for all SILLs.

Figure 16 – Overall concept map of LCC detailing each step

5.5 Hotspot Analysis

A hotspot can be identified at various levels of granularity: life cycle stage, process, or elementary flow. A hotspot is defined as (1) all life cycle stages, (2) all processes and (3) all elementary flows contributing at least 50% to any impact category before normalization and weighting. The most relevant impact categories are also identified. Hotspot analysis methodological steps are shown in Figure 17 and represent a complementary assessment viewpoint to the LCA, LCC, and SLCA.

With a hotspot analysis the following questioned would be asked to the SILLs.

- Where and when are the most emission or most significant costs incurred across the life cycle of the SILL?
- What are the most consequential resources (energy, raw materials, and water etc.) consumed throughout the life cycle?
- Where are resources being wasted or underutilized and if there is a chance to optimize the resources
- Where are the toxic chemicals used, and how are they prevented from impacting the environment or human health?
- How does the value chain impact different ZeroW stakeholders?
- Which stakeholders positively/negatively benefited and impacted from the innovation, and which were negatively impacted?
- How could greater value be derived?³³

Figure 17 - Eight key methodological steps for hotspot analysis

³³ <http://unep.ecoinnovation.org/activities/st6/>

After finding the hotspots from the assessment it is important to engage the stakeholders, disseminate the result and solicitate the agreement on collective expertise, either validate or rearrange the goal and scope for the sustainability assessment.

Hotspot analysis is crucial that being used around the world the address sustainability challenges to identify the area of overload. However, there is not standard method or framework to hotspot analysis. Methodology developed by SETAC gives a common methodological framework and guidance to hotspot analysis which will be further illustrated under ZeroW assessment framework (T5.2).⁸

5.6 LCSA in a nutshell

In ZeroW, the decision-makers, policy makers, internal & external stakeholders, enterprises, and consumers will benefit from the LCSA and hotspot analysis as it will: (i) organise complex environmental, economic, and social data in a structured form, making data reuse, curation, and preservation easier; (ii) clarify the trade-offs between the three sustainability pillars, providing a comprehensive picture of the positive and negative impacts that each SILL processes and services bring out; (iii) support enterprises and value chain actors involved in the SILLs to identify weaknesses and improve the impacts of the demonstrated innovations. The data collection mechanism for LCSA is centrally described in Section 7.

6. Cost Benefit Analysis and Balance

CBA is a systemic process that measures the benefits of an action or a decision subtracting the associated costs. Therefore, CBA allows entities to assess which decision to make and which to forego. In numeric terms, a CBA when performed provides measurable financial metrics, e.g., revenue generation or cost savings because of a decision or an action to pursue. More complex analysis may also include – (a) intangible benefits or costs (e.g., customer satisfaction), (b) sensitivity analysis, (c) discounting of cashflows, and (d) what-if scenario analysis.

In the context of the ZeroW project, CBA will assess the financial feasibility of the systemic innovations deployed in the nine SILLs and their long-term economic sustainability, therefore it is complementary to LCC assessment. In line with the “Guide to Cost-Benefit Analysis of Investment Projects” published by the EC³⁴, the analytical framework of performing CBA in the ZeroW project incorporates three characteristics and requirements –

- Analysis of the investment and costs associated with the SILLs.
- CBA to be carried out in a long-term economic sustainability perspective.
- Assessment of economic performance to be expressed in quantitative figures for value of the investment and its economic returns.

The CBA proposed in ZeroW will assess and evaluate the SILLs on a five-year time horizon beyond which the investment should create an added value for the SILL stakeholders. The evaluation will be performed using three indicators –

- **Internal Return Rate (IRR)** – it measures the investment efficiency; higher the value of IRR for a SILL, higher is its desirability.
- **Net Present Value (NPV)** – it calculates the benefit and cost cash flow measuring the performance of a SILL in terms of investment.
- **Benefit to cost ratio**

While there is no standardised methodology to perform CBA, the steps undertaken in current literature and previous European funded projects (e.g., AEOLIX, CO-GISTICS) for CBA have only minor differentiation. The ZeroW CBA methodology (shown in Figure 18) is based upon the steps reported by AEOLIX project³⁵ and has been further adopted for the systemic innovation and SILL perspectives.

³⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/sources/docgener/studies/pdf/cba_guide.pdf

³⁵ AEOLIX project (Grant Agreement Number: 690797) Deliverable 8.5 - Cost – Benefit Analysis

Figure 18 – Methodological steps for CBA in ZeroW

For each SILL, end users are identified in WP4 and WP7. End user identification will cluster them into specific groups followed by identification of costs and benefits through scouting business cases for each SILL, each group, and type of transactions. The costs and benefits will then be categorised by user, SILL category, and year followed by their financial valuation as it is the most crucial aspect of the entire CBA. Calculations of the three above-mentioned indicators will be then performed along with an aggregated analysis for all SILLs. That will lead to further economic

sustainability interpretation and recommendations for all SILLs. The data collection necessary for the CBA is described in Section 7.

Propositioning ZeroW's CBA in line with the JRC report published in⁹, the aggregated analysis step in Figure 18 will evaluate the following aspects –

- **Net economic benefits** achieved by SILLs – For example, SILLs dealing with donation of surplus food products, net economic benefits consider adding economic value of the avoided purchase of food to avoided cost of food waste disposal while subtracting cost of the donation action.
- **Net environmental savings** – It is calculated considering three aspects – (a) environmental impacts linked to producing the food no longer purchased, (b) environmental impacts linked to the waste treatment operations that would have taken place had the food been wasted, and (c) environmental impacts caused by implementing the action.
- **Net social benefits** – It is calculated considering the poverty (number of meals donated), social inclusion, new skill development, job creation, consumer awareness etc.

7. Data Collection

The goal of the assessment is to analyse the “As is” and “To be” phases of the SILLs. Collecting data is an integral part of the methodology, hence an explicit guideline to collect data during the SILLs’ life cycle is dedicated to section 7. This section serves as a guideline to various stages, methods, and plan of action for data collection. It also illustrates on diverse types of data from primary and secondary data sources.

7.1 Different stages of data collection

WP5 will lead the data collection in several stages and will liaise with WP4 during the process.

The first stage of the data collection covers an awareness and education phase for the SILL members. During this stage, the intention and procedure of collecting data will be demonstrated in a form of one-to-one workshop with maximum number of active members from each SILL (coordinator, operational head, financial and CSR expert). The expected outcome of the workshop is to provide information about what type of data WP5 is looking for, who is the responsible person to provide that data to WP5, what are the risks and challenges SILL would face to provide those data and the mitigation plan to move forward.

The second stage of the data collection is dedicated to select relevant KPI, as explained in previous chapters, there are international standards to select impact categories (LCA, LCC, SLCA) and number of KPI are available for the assessment. On that account it is crucial to select relevant KPIs based on assumption. The number of KPI can change as the assessment progresses adding more KPIs to the evaluation. The expected outcome from the meeting is the selected KPI and the identification of the possible data points to measure those KPI. The participants are mostly like the first set of data collection.

In the third stage of data collection SILLs will be assigned to provide baseline information based on their current readiness level. This stage is pivotal to determine the ‘before’ situation for each SILL and is based on a format of template/survey questionnaire. Stage 4 and 5 will be engage to collect data during the project life time. Since data collection is an iterative process, similar steps can be repeated during the process. A tentative timeline for data collection is given in Figure 19.

Table 5 - An overview of data collection in ZeroW

Data Collection	Activities	Purpose	Outcome	Participants	Method
1st stage	Guideline on data collection	Awareness and Education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Build collective understanding on data collection Identify the responsible SILL members Identify the risks and have mitigation policies 	SILL coordinator, Operation specialist, Finance & CSR expert/HR	Workshop
2nd stage	Selection of KPI and data points	Selection of KPI and data points	Listed KPI And data points	SILL coordinator, Operation specialist, Finance & CSR expert/HR	Workshop
3rd stage	Baseline data collection ³⁶	Preliminary investigation	Baseline data	Responsible SILL members from each department	Template/ Survey/ Interview/ Document scrutinization
4th stage	Mid-term data collection	Measure the progress of SI	Data during the implementation of innovative solution	Responsible SILL members	Template/ Survey/ Interview/ Document Scrutinization / Lab visit (if needed)
5th stage	End-point data collection	Measure the improvement Of SI	Data after implementing innovative solution at a mature level	Responsible SILL members	Template/ Survey/ Interview (Lab/Farm visit if needed)

³⁶ Annex III

7.2 Types of Data

The generation of reliable data is essential in LCA, however, collecting data can be tedious. Primary data will come from the SILLs through template, survey analysis, interview, document collection scrutinization and lab or farm visit etc. The format for creating primary database can be offline (excel, paper) web-based (Google docs, survey money, Enketo etc.) However, at an incredibly early stage of SILL demonstration data uncertainty is evident hence the use of secondary data necessary. Secondary data can be collected from

- Literature
- Standard database (A list of databases is given in Annex -VI)

7.3 Timeline of data collection in ZeroW

Figure 19 - Timeline for data collection

Monte Carlo Analysis

Having numerous novel technologies in each SILL and a broad array of sustainability in the food supply chain, uncertainty of inventory data, unavoidable errors in the data collection process can be a recurrent issue during the SILL lifecycle. To solve the issue of uncertainty it is recommended that to use the Monte Carlo analysis. The Monte Carlo method, also known as statistical simulation method, is a very precise method of numerical calculation guided by probability statistical theory by the use of uncertain variables based on probabilistic analysis, and combination with the pre-determined impact assessment method to simulate, so as to obtain statistically

significant environmental impact evaluation results, which can reflect the influence of uncertain factors more accurately.³⁷

Few key points to success

- Performing a screening level approach to get order of the magnitude of results
- Having a detailed analysis to refine results and most important contributors
- An explicit system boundary focusing on three pillar approaches
- A quantified FU
- Improved data quality as the success of the study depends on the quality of the data used
- Detailed stakeholder assessment
- Detailed cost analysis (production, waste etc.)
- Compare different impact methods
- Analyse contributions at various levels
- Provide scenario analysis

A template for base line data collection is given in Annex - III which will be further developed in T5.2.

³⁷ Sun, S. and Ertz, M., 2020. Life cycle assessment and Monte Carlo simulation to evaluate the environmental impact of promoting LNG vehicles. *MethodsX*, 7, p.101046

8. Conclusion

The aim of the tools and the methodology is to provide a way of continuously assessing the systemic innovations and SILLs. Overall, it helps to track performance and improve the SI design, resource optimization leading towards a sustainable solution for the planet. ZeroW's iterative assessment methodology signifies a continuous improvements approach for the SILLs. It will systematise a culture of continuous evolution that entails moving forward towards innovative sustainable development by setting up reference implementations, benchmarks, and sustainable cooperations among the SILLs.

The outputs of the SURL, LCSA, and CBA assessment metrics will be combined, paving way for assessing the levels of just allocation of costs, benefits, and risks among food value chain actors. This analysis will be further extended for select regions (in Task 5.3), following the Just Transition Mechanism paradigm³⁸, to also feed the scaling up strategies in WP6.

³⁸ https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal/actions-being-taken-eu/just-transition-mechanism/justtransition-funding-sources_en

9. Annex I: SIRL Tools sample Questions

Discuss with SILL members whether this dimension is important to consider. If so, why? Make use of the questions below to prompt the discussion. Be as specific as possible. Specify/refine/rephrase the scope of the behavioural dimensions, and define sub-dimensions (e.g., knowledge/socio-cultural/other) if this is considered useful for following-up the SI process in the future.

1. Is the mindset (of the public, involved actors, investors, policy makers, end users, etc.) ready for adoption, implementation, diffusion, and scaling of the FLW solution?
2. Are there any issues regarding knowledge levels that might hamper SI development and/or the readiness for adoption, uptake, diffusion, and scaling of the FLW solution?
3. Are there any issues regarding prevailing (implicit) norms, informal rules, beliefs, values, attitudes, etc. that might hamper the SI development and/or the readiness for adoption, diffusion, and scaling of the FLW solution?
4. When exploring potential issues in the behavioural domain, ask the question: what is the issue exactly? How exactly is the issue expected to impact the SI process of the SILL? Describe the detected issue as precisely as possible (= this is the starting point of SIRL step 2, since this formulation/description corresponds to either level 1 or 2 of the corresponding RL, depending on the level of detail. Level 1 is the acknowledgement of the existence of an issue; level 2 is the formulation of the issue)
5. Are the detected issues in the behavioural domain limited to a certain group, or do they apply to the whole society?
6. Do the detected issues apply to the current situation, or do they include potential future pitfalls?
7. What obstacles does the issue cause for the development, implementation, and/or scaling up of the FLW solution?
8. How severe is this problem regarding the development, uptake, and scaling of the solution?
9. How to tackle it? (□ this answer may influence the readiness levels to be used)
10. Is there a need for a behavioural innovation (= e.g., altering consumer behaviours through a new way of nudging, changing visions/beliefs using a new type of communication campaign, etc.) to support the implementation and scaling of the FLW solution?

If it remains unclear whether there is an issue in this dimension that needs to be tackled, should the SILL act to further explore this dimension? For example, by involving or consulting someone with expertise? If yes, discuss what actions to take and who is responsible.

10. Annex II: Preliminary System Boundary of SILLs

Figure 20 – Preliminary system boundary of SILL 1

Figure 21 - Preliminary system boundary of SILL 2

Figure 22 - Preliminary system boundary of SILL 3

Figure 23 - Preliminary system boundary of SILL 4

Figure 24 - Preliminary system boundary of SILL 5

Figure 25 - Preliminary system boundary of SILL 6

Figure 26 - Preliminary system boundary of SILL 7

Figure 27 - Preliminary system boundary of SILL 8

Figure 28 - Preliminary system boundary of SILL 9

11. Annex III: Template to calculate base value

**Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment
and Cost Benefit Analysis
Template for data collection for
SILLs**

Aims

- Inform SILL about the data they are required to collect
- Align with SILL about the data they can provide, and which data will be collected from public sources (secondary data)
- Awareness and education level

For evaluating SILL's progress is crucial to define objectives (impact) and indicators before the implementation and know what the baseline (FLW generated in the value chain today) is. The baseline will be used to monitor the progress and success of SILL work in the project. Assessment will provide SILL impacts, risk, sustainability trade-offs and level of 'just' allocation, not only at the end of the project but yearly to track progress towards a target and quantify sustainability benefits.

Data collection

All SILLs will be asked to collect data for 1 year time. They will be encouraged to provide as much information as it is possible. Before the assessment questionnaire is developed, each SILL's alignment will be provided to assess the information SILLs can provide and not rely on secondary data unless it is unavoidable.

Assessment

Based on Caldeira et al. 2020,⁹ assessment of SILLs' impact on the reduction of FLW, the assessment will be based on economic, social and environmental savings considering both the burden and benefits of the actions:

- A) Environmental, social, and economic impacts of avoided food production
- B) Environmental, social, and economic impact of avoided food waste management
- C) Environmental, social, and economic impact of the implementation of the action.

Based on holistically assessed impacts, SILLs are individually evaluated, indicators are tailored according to the type of action, and all sustainability aspects are considered. Their individual questionnaires will be built upon systemic boundaries and functional units.

Objectives

FLW target: Reduction target in percent

Baseline against which progress towards the goal of the action was assessed in kg:

Firstly, we will assess the baseline, and current state at M13, before any implementation of the SILL's systemic innovations takes place.

Amount of FLW prevented in kg: _____

Stages of the supply chain where food waste was prevented and amounted in kg:

- Primary production
- Processing and manufacturing
- Retail and other distribution of food
- Restaurants and food services sector
- Households

Cost of implemented action implementation:

What is the value of avoided food waste?

Had food waste been generated, what would be the treatment process:

- Anaerobic digestion
- Composting
- Incineration
- Landfill
- Other

Cost of waste disposal?

Indicators and data

Depending on their system boundaries, the SILLs will provide data for various stages of the food supply chain. But all SILL will need data for FLW. Assessments questionnaire will be provided for T5.2, here are presented only basic requirements so that SILLs can be prepared for the data required.

Crop base data, 1 hectare, 1 year of production.

Country	Name of the country, region e.g., Italy, Umbria			
	Input or activity	Compound name	Amount applied/consumed/produced	
			kg per hectare per year	€ per hectare per year
Soil carbon	Soil type			
	Soil ploughed?			

	Specific practices?			
	workforce (soil preparation)			
Seeds	Seeds input			
	workforce (sowing)			
Fertilisation	Fertiliser-N (type 1)	e.g., ammonium nitrate		
	Fertiliser-N (type 2)			
	Fertiliser-N (type 3)			
	Fertiliser-P2O5 (type 1)			
	Fertiliser-P2O5 (type 2)			
	Fertiliser-P2O5 (type 3)			
	Fertiliser-K2O (type 1)			
	Fertiliser-K2O (type 2)			
	Fertiliser-K2O (type 3)			
	Organic input	e.g., cattle manure, slurry, digestate, compost...		
	Lime	CaCO ₃ /MgCO ₃		
	Sulphur			
	How many fertilizer applications?			
	workforce			
Crop protection	Herbicides	if known		
	Fungicides	if known		
	Pesticides	if known		
	Plastic, fleece, etc			
	workforce			
Energy	Diesel			
	Petrol			
	Electricity			
	Other			
Water	Water			
	Water source			
	Irrigation type			
	workforce			
Outputs	Primary product output (in the fresh matter)			
	Co-product output 1			
	Co-product output 2			

	Co-product output 3			
	Co-product output 4			
	Co-product output 5			
	Co-product output 6			
	Co-product output 7			
	Co-product output 8			
	Co-product output 9			
	Co-product output 10			
			
Interactions				
total workforce for the crop		hour/total production (kg)		

Farm level

Country	Name of the country, region	e.g., Slovenia	Amount applied/consumed/produced	
			kg per hectare per year	€ per hectare per year
	Input or activity	Compound name		
Soil carbon	Soil type			
	Soil ploughed?			
	Specific practices?			
	workforce (soil preparation)			
Seeds	Seeds input			
	workforce (sowing)			
Fertilisation	Fertiliser-N (type 1)	e.g., ammonium nitrate		
	Fertiliser-N (type 2)			
	Fertiliser-N (type 3)			
	Fertiliser-P2O5 (type 1)			
	Fertiliser-P2O5 (type 2)			
	Fertiliser-P2O5 (type 3)			
	Fertiliser-K2O (type 1)			

	Fertiliser-K2O (type 2)			
	Fertiliser-K2O (type 3)			
	Organic input	e.g., cattle manure, slurry, digestate, compost		
	Lime	CaCO3/MgCO3		
	Sulphur			
	How many fertilizer applications?			
	workforce			
Crop protection	Herbicides	if known		
	Fungicides	if known		
	Pesticides	if known		
	Plastic, fleece, etc			
	workforce			
Energy	Diesel			
	Petrol			
	Electricity			
Water	Water			
	Water source			
	Irrigation type			
	workforce			
Outputs	Primary product output (in the fresh matter)			
	Co-product output 1			
	Co-product output 2			
	Co-product output 3			
	Co-product output 4			
	Co-product output 5			
	Co-product output 6			
	Co-product output 7			
	Co-product output 8			
	Co-product output 9			
	Co-product output 10			
			
Revenue	Returns from crops			
	Returns from animals	<i>if any</i>		
	Government program payments			

	Other farm income			
Expenses	Farm Operating Expenses			
	Interest payments			

Value chain

Final Product	Final product	e.g., 500 g tomatoes, packaged	
	Input or activity	Amount	
		per tonne ex farm gate	€ per tonne ex farm gate
Preliminary processing	Country	e.g., Slovenia	
	Dry matter content	% Fresh weight	
	Drying	Yes/No	
	Cooling	Yes/No	
	workforce		
Transport	Transport 1	km	
	Transport 2	km	
	Transport 3	km	
	Waste losses (spoilage)	%	
	workforce		
Processing energy	Country	e.g., Slovenia	
	Oil	Litres	
	Gas	m3 or kWh	
	Coal	kg	
	Wood	kg	
	Electricity	kWh	
	Other		
	Waste losses (spoilage)	%	
Processing other inputs	Water	Litres	
	Another raw materials 1	kg fresh matter	
	Another raw materials 2	kg fresh matter	

	Another raw materials 3	kg fresh matter	
Processing outputs	Wastewater	Litres	
	Co-product 1	kg	
	Co-product 2	kg	
	Co-product 3	kg	
Packaging	Country	e.g., Slovenia	
	Packaging type 1	kg	
	Packaging type 2	kg	
	Packaging type 3	kg	
	workforce		
Transport	Transport 1	km	
	Transport 2	km	
	Transport 3	km	
	Waste losses (spoilage)	%	
	workforce		
Distribution	Country	e.g., Slovenia	
	Oil	Litres	
	Gas	m3 or kWh	
	Coal	kg	
	Wood	kg	
	Electricity	kWh	
	Other		
	Waste losses (spoilage)	%	
	workforce		
Consumption	Country	e.g., Slovenia	
	Oil	Litres	
	Gas	m3 or kWh	
	Coal	kg	
	Wood	kg	
	Electricity	kWh	
	Other		
	Waste losses (spoilage)	%	

Value chain economic data:

Name of the country, region	e.g., Slovenia			
			unit	Notes
diameter in which VC actors are located, excluding consumers				
Workforce	nb of workers		FTE	
	nb of employees		FTE	
Workforce cost			euro	
VC actors perception				
Final products and co-products	price/unit			
Funds			euro	
Firm debts			euro	
Private debt			euro	
(Off-firm income)			euro	
Revenue			euro	
Investments			euro	
Liquidity reserve (household and farm)			euro	
Taxes			euro	
Total production costs/Variable costs			euro	
Average total assets			euro	
Total costs of inputs per product?			for the 5 last years	
Total costs of each activity?			for the 5 last years	
Total profit			for the 5 last years	
Potential constraints from suppliers and buyers?				
What are the key factors of success?				
Constraints from policies?				
Constraints from bio-physical context?				
Distance between activities' location VC			euro	
Consumers	type	percentage	distances	
1	e.g., local community			
2	e.g., tourists			
3	e.g., remote consumers			
4				

Social indicators

Nutritional value of FLW:

What are the key stakeholders in your value chain? Quadruple helix model.

Which are the actors that benefit from your solution, and which actors will pay for it?

Poverty – number of meals donated

Unemployment – number of jobs created

Social inclusion – involvement of individuals and groups to improve the situation in society:

New skills – number of people who developed new competencies while taking part in the SILLS

12. Annex IV – Impact category for environmental footprint

Impact category	Indicator	Unit
Climate Change	Radiative forcing as Global Warming Potential (GWP100)	kg CO ₂ eq
Ozone depletion	Ozone Depletion Potential (ODP)	kg CFC-11 eq
Human toxicity, non-cancer effects	Comparative Toxic Unit for humans (CTU _h)	CTU _h
Human toxicity, cancer effects	Comparative Toxic Unit for humans (CTU _h)	CTU _h
Particulate matter	Human health effects associated with exposure to PM _{2.5}	Disease incidences
Ionizing radiation, human health	Human exposure efficiency relative to U ²³⁵	kBq U ²³⁵
Photochemical ozone formation, human health	Tropospheric ozone concentration increase	kg NMVOC eq
Acidification	Accumulated Exceedance (AE)	mol H ⁺ eq
Terrestrial eutrophication	Accumulated Exceedance (AE)	mol N eq
Freshwater eutrophication	Fraction of nutrients reaching freshwater end compartment (P)	kg P eq
Marine eutrophication	Fraction of nutrients reaching marine end compartment (N)	kg N eq
Freshwater ecotoxicity	Comparative Toxic Unit for ecosystems (CTU _e)	CTU _e
Land use	Soil quality index	Pt
Water use	User deprivation potential (deprivation weighted water consumption)	m ³ world eq. deprived
Resource use, fossil	Abiotic resource depletion – fossil fuels (ADP-fossil)	MJ
Resource use, minerals and metals	Abiotic resource depletion (ADP ultimate reserves)	kg Sb eq

Environmental Footprint impact categories, table taken from Fazio et al. (2018)

Overall UNEP/SETAC scheme of the environmental LCIA framework, linking LCI results via the midpoint categories to damage categories (adapted from Jolliet et al., 2003a).

13. Annex V – Sustainability Development Goals

1 NO POVERTY 	Fair salary Poverty alleviation	7 AFFORDABLE AND CLEAN ENERGY 	Access to material resources	13 CLIMATE ACTION 	
2 ZERO HUNGER 	Access to material resources	8 DECENT WORK AND ECONOMIC GROWTH 	Freedom of association Child labor Forced labor Working hours Social benefits/security Local employment Fair salary Contributions to economic development Employment relationship	14 LIFE BELOW WATER 	
3 GOOD HEALTH AND WELL-BEING 	Health and safety (W & C) Human health issues Safe healthy living Health issues for children as consumers	9 INDUSTRY, INNOVATION AND INFRASTRUCTURE 	Access to material resources Technology development	15 LIFE ON LAND 	
4 QUALITY EDUCATION 	Access to immaterial resources Education provided to the local community	10 REDUCED INEQUALITIES 	Indigenous rights Delocalization & migration Equal opportunity / discrimination Wealth distribution	16 PEACE, JUSTICE AND STRONG INSTITUTIONS 	Legal system corruption Prevention and mitigation of armed conflicts Delocalization and migration Access to immaterial resources Secure living conditions
5 GENDER EQUALITY 	Equal opportunity / discrimination Sexual harassment	11 SUSTAINABLE CITIES AND COMMUNITIES 	Cultural heritage Community engagement Capacity building	17 PARTNERSHIPS FOR THE GOALS 	Public commitment to sustainability issues
6 CLEAN WATER AND SANITATION 	Access to material resources	12 RESPONSIBLE CONSUMPTION AND PRODUCTION 	Fair competition Supplier relationships Promoting social responsibility Respect for intellectual property rights Feedback mechanism Transparency Consumer privacy End of life responsibility Children conscious regarding marketing practices Ethical treatment of animals		

The S-LCA impact subcategories linked to the 17 SDGs. Most prominent ones are presented.

14. Annex VI – Relevant Databases for LCA

Database name	Source	Available Region	Cost
Swiss National LCI Database ecoinvent	http://www.ecoinvent.org/	Europe	commercial
GaBi software database	http://www.gabi-software.com/databases/	Europe	commercial
The European Union's European Reference life-cycle Data System ELCD	http://eplca.jrc.ec.europa.eu/	Europe	free
LCA food database	http://www.lcafood.dk/	Europe	free
SimaPro software database	https://simapro.com/about/	Europe	commercial
openLCA software database	https://www.openlca.org/	Europe	free